

DEVELOPMENT OF INFANCY IN YOUNG PERIODS

Kutlimuratova Azodaxan ,

*2nd year student of Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh,
Faculty of Practical Psychology*

Qalmuratova Shaxlo ,

*3rd year student of Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh,
Faculty of Foreign Languages*

Abstract: *This article discusses the psychological characteristics of preschool children. The higher psyche that appears in children especially during infancy. Features of the appearance of functions are widely covered.*

Key words: *infancy, early childhood, preschool age, thinking, emotion, perception, will, intellect.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7675377>

Studying the scientific and theoretical aspects of the psychological characteristics of children of early childhood and preschool age is of great practical importance in higher pedagogical education. In this context, it should be noted that society is a set of problems of people, including children. The development and spiritual potential of a democratic society is largely determined by the psychological and educational education given to these children. As each child lives in society, he strives to occupy a unique place and an independent position in it, therefore, he demonstrates his own aspirations, abilities and activity, and examples of intellectual work. There are a number of pedagogical sciences that study mutual relations between children and the role of each individual in society and the nature of his various social relations, among which psychology occupies a special place.

There are different ways of classifying age periods in psychology. This approach to the study of the human personality from different points of view and illuminates the nature of this problem in different ways. Swiss psychologist J. Piaget's theory of mind, functions of mind and includes the doctrine of his times. The main tasks of intelligence are adaptation and habituation, which is its permanent set of tasks. The author, following mental development of the child's intelligence classified into periods:

1. sensorimotor intelligence - from birth to 2 years;
2. preoperative thinking period - from 2 to 7 years;
3. period of specific operations - from 7.8 to 11, 12 years;
4. period of official operations.

The French psychologist A. Vallon divides the age periods into the following stages. separates:

- 1) the period of the fetus in the mother's womb;
- 2) period of impulsive action - from birth to 6 months;

- 3) period of feelings (emotional) - from 1 month to 1 year;
- 4) sensomogor (coordination of perception and movement) period from 1 to 3 years;
- 5) the period of personology (becoming a person) - from 3 to 5 years old; 19
- 6) period of differentiation - from 6 to 11 years;
- 7) puberty and adolescence - from 12 to 18 years.

L.S. Vygotsky critically analyzed the theories of the classification of young age periods of psychologists, relying on mental updates that create certain development divides age periods into the following stages;

1. Childhood crisis.
2. Infancy period - from 2 months to 1 year, one-year crisis.
3. Early childhood - from 1 to 3 years - crisis of 3 years.
4. Preschool period - from 3 to 7 years - 7 years crisis.
5. School age period - from 8 to 12 years - 13 years crisis.
6. Puberty (sexual maturity) period - age crisis from 14 to 18 years.

L.S. Vygotsky was able to scientifically base and describe his theory of stratification of young people. The scientist made scientific and practical comments about the most important psychic updates. However, there are also very controversial and valuable points in these comments. In general, L.S. Vygotsky's theory of the classification of youth periods has scientific historical significance, its development his thoughtful and advanced ideas about crises are in line with the requirements of the present day.

The period of infancy includes the period from birth to one year of age, during which the child is born with a mature nervous system to adapt to the external environment. The period of infancy is the organic needs of human life (to oxygen, food, heat or cold) is the only period in which innate, instinctive forms of behavior directed towards satisfaction are observed in their pure form. Human behavior, incomparable opportunities to acquire new experiences are the main characteristics of children in infancy. If the organic needs are sufficiently satisfied, they lose their primary importance: as a result of the correctly externalized routine, regime and upbringing, the child becomes the basis for the mental development of the child. a set of needs arises. From the first week of birth, a child's senses of sight and hearing develop rapidly. The child begins to observe the moving object. He begins to pay attention to different sounds, including the voices of adults. A newborn's brain weighs $\frac{1}{4}$ of an adult's brain, and the number of nerve cells is the same as an adult's, but they are enough will not be developed. Early infancy is a child's defenseless, less active, more active state is the period of becoming a rapidly developing, cheerful child. He establishes relationships with adults in a short time²³, is able to grasp objects and use them learns He observes things in the world around him, tries to find out what they are like by holding objects with his hands, pays attention to sounds, and with the help of objects tries to create sounds by himself. He has an emotional relationship with his mother and other relatives. A child of infant age, both physically and mentally, also develops very quickly socially. In a very short time, from a child with very little reaction to the events around him, to an active, quick-witted, mobile helper turns into a child who can call, who is happy when adults come near.

A child's life during infancy is completely connected with the emotional relationship with adults, which directly affects the child's mood. From the age of 4-5 months, the child begins to distinguish his relatives from strangers. The emotional relationship with adults is the main leading activity of children of this age and is considered the basis of the child's mental development. The constant presence of adults with the child, in relation to him getting used to the didactic focus can lead to a decrease in his interest in toys. Proper upbringing leads to the exchange of the child's relationship with adults with objects and toys. All actions performed with the help of adults are the basis for the future mental development of the child. Adults emotional attitude towards the child, the child's attention to their words, trying to respond, remembering some words and expressing emotion means the development of attention, memory, speech and other cognitive processes. Normal color separation in a child from the age of two months, from 3-4 months.

From the age of 2 months, the baby begins to distinguish his mother's face and voice from those of others. From 2-3 months, he responds to his mother's smile and laughter with a smile and various actions. From the age of 3-4 months, children show their loved ones that they want to be seen, heard or spoken to by their actions, and from the age of 8 months, the child shows his anxiety by crying when he is in a strange environment and in the hands of strangers. This anxiety gradually begins to decrease at the age of 14-18 months. In 2-3-month-old children, the formation of the movements of grasping objects leads to the development of their perception of the shape and size of objects. A child who has reached the age of one has an interest in learning about the environment and a developing cognitive activity.

Growing age, the laws of mental processes in human development, the leading factors in it, and the characteristics of a person's personality at different stages of a person's life are the research subjects of the psychology of youth. It is known that a person does not fully understand the psychological laws of the formation process, its scientific foundations, and the theoretical and practical aspects of education and upbringing practical issues cannot be solved successfully. This is the age without researching the psychological characteristics that appear especially during infancy

it is impossible to eliminate the various problems that appear during the period.

REFERENCES

1. Goziyev, E. (2010). Umumiy psixologiya. Yangi asr avlodi.
2. Davletshin, M. (2002). Umumiy psixologiya. TDPU.
3. Suyarov, A. (2017). The present condition of tourism in Samarkand, the results of research survey from tourists in region. SCOPE Acad. HOUSE BM Publ. 103, 41-46.
4. Samarova Shoxista Rabidjanovna, Rakhmonova Muqaddas Qahramanovna, Mirzarahimova Gulnora, Ikromovna, Maratov Temur Gayrat ugli, Kamilov Bobir Sultanovich. (2020). Psychological aspects of developing creative personality and the concept of reduction of creativity to intellect. JCR. 7(17): 498-505. doi: 10.31838/jcr.07.17.69
5. Jabbor Usarov. (2019, June). Using Teaching Methods for Development Pupil Competencies. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies, 15(1), 272-274.

6. Jabbor Eshbekovich Usarov. (2017). Formation Competence at Pupils as the Factor of Increase of Education's Efficiency. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, 53(9), 79-82.
7. Mukhamedov Gafurdjan Isroilovich, & Usarov Djabbar Eshbekovich. (2020). Technologies for the Development of Competencies in Physics in General Secondary Education using Multimedia Resources. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 9(3), 2677-2684.
8. Usarov Djabbar Eshkulovich, & Suyarov Kusharbay Tashbaevich. (2020). Developing Pupils' Learning and Research Skills on the Basis of Physical Experiments. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(02), 1337-1346.
9. Maratov Temur Gayrat ugli (2019) Scientific theoretical problems of perfect human category in the psychology. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*. 7(8). 16-22.
10. NJ Əshnaev, TG' Maratov, G Mirzaraximova. (2020). O'zbek milliy kino san'ati va madaniyatida psixoprofilaktik xizmat tizimini joriy etish masalalari. *Oriental Art and Culture* 03. 156-165.
11. Murodinova, N., & Ganiyeva, M. The role of family to develop for perfect person. <http://baziz.uz/upload/third/18-21%20MART%20-%20Murodinova%20&%20Ganiyeva.pdf>